

Technical paper

Advancing human-robot collaboration: Predicting operator trajectories through AI and infrared imaging

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ABSTRACT

In industrial applications demanding close interaction between humans and robots, accurate perception of the robot's surroundings is vital to adjust its behavior appropriately. This need becomes especially pertinent when manipulators operate autonomously and execute both separate and common tasks with human operators. To ensure operator safety in such Human-Robot Collaboration (HRC) environments, the present paper proposes an innovative approach that leverages advanced collaborative robotic systems capable of sensing the operator's position to effectively prevent or mitigate potential contact. Our solution combines infrared-thermal imaging technology with a workspace monitoring system, utilizing thermal and depth cameras, to track the operator's current location and predict their future trajectory using a multi-layer Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network. We also introduce a technique for simulating both human and robot movements to generate a synthetic dataset. This data is shared with the motion planning system to generate trajectories that do not intersect with the operator's future paths, minimizing downtime due to safety stoppages. The solution is integrated and evaluated within an industrial high payload collaborative robot context, and the results have shown improvements in cycle time efficiency and operator approval. This approach offers a promising direction for enhancing safety and productivity in HRC workspaces.

1. Introduction

Over the last years the need for the implementation of flexible and reconfigurable production systems, that are capable of producing highly customized products of different production sizes [1], has driven the research attention into designing and deploying human-robot collaborative (HRC) cells. The seamless, tight existence and collaboration between robotic manipulators and human operators, achieves the combination of the advantages of both aspects; the speed, accuracy, and facile weightlifting of robots with the flexibility, creativity, and dexterity of humans [2].

The integration of HRC (Human-Robot Collaboration) systems introduces significant challenges, particularly concerning safety aspects to ensure the operators' protection. [3,4]. When humans and robots closely interact, strict safety measures are applied to limit the robot's speed and force, especially in power and force-limiting applications. To prevent operators from entering hazardous areas, fail-safe sensors such as laser scanners, safety mats, light barriers, and safety camera systems monitor

the workspace [4]. These sensors establish either a static safety zone layout or, in some cases, dynamically changing zones based on relevant robot orientation [5]. However, the discretization level allows only predefined robot motion programs. Non-fail-safe approaches using conventional RGB cameras or RGBD sensors [6] have been proposed to track operators' positions in the workspace with good accuracy. However, these approaches require higher computational power and perform poorly in low-light conditions. In contrast, thermal cameras form the environment's imagery based solely on emitted thermal energy, independent of light conditions, offering a robust solution for varying light and weather conditions [7,8]. To maximize the potential of both human and robotic resources, robots also need to possess cognitive abilities to comprehend their surroundings and human actions. Beyond this, predicting human intentions will allow robots to adapt their actions to optimize collaborative efficiency.

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1.1. Human detection using IR technology

This advantage of thermal cameras has led to their application in numerous sectors where there is need for detecting humans [9]. Such examples may be found in automotive related safety applications for pedestrians and vehicles [10–12], in military applications for detecting e.g., snipers [13], in search and rescue applications where UAVs (Unmanned Aerial Vehicle) and rescue robots are deployed with Infra-Red (IR) cameras searching for people during natural disasters or terrorist occurrences [14]. Applications of IR cameras may be found in supervision systems that perform human detection, tracking and analyze his/her behavior acting proactively in cases of suspicious actions preventing potential intrusions [9]. General human activity analysis has also been studied, e.g., for separating walking and running spatio-temporal information [15] analysis of human posture in case somebody is lying down [16].

1.2. Operator motion prediction

Human intention recognition is a focal point of research in multiple fields. A significant hurdle faced by researchers is the stochastic nature of human behavior. Most methodologies employ Artificial Intelligence, using neural networks trained on real, synthetic, or mixed data. Application examples include pedestrian avoidance that are used for autonomous vehicles [17], task identification through visual observation of hand-object interaction [18,19], gesture-based command recognition used for AGVs controls [20], EEG-based recognition of human intentions [21], and context-based human motion recognition [22–24]. They also cover synchronization of HRC tasks by estimating human hand motion and syncing it with robot end-effector motion [25].

Specifically, for the estimation of humans' future trajectory Rudenko et al. [26] have made an extensive study where they cover in depth the motion prediction problem and decompose it in higher lever, in two main directions; one based in modelling approach, and one based on contextual cues. The categorization of human motion prediction approaches is based on how they represent human movement and formulate the underlying causes of that movement. Physics-based approaches may include single or multiple dynamic, physics-based models. Pattern-based approaches learn movement patterns from the observed agent paths, using sequential or non-sequential predictive models. Planning-based approaches reason on motion intents of sensible agents and include forward or inverse planning methods in a sense to compute a path hypothesis [26].

2. Approach and architecture

2.1. IR-based human tracking

In the present study, human position detection was performed using various sensors placed in different layout, as this information is very important to be shared among the safety related and path planning modules. The approach followed, consists of depth sensors with

integrated software SDK for human pose detection (Azure Kinect + Azure Kinect Body Tracking SDK) which is plug and play from Microsoft, and a custom-made IR camera based human tracking software which is analyzed in the manuscript. The overall detection pipeline, which is summarized in Fig. 1, consists of 4 main pillars. The first pillar is related to the sensing layer which corresponds to the data acquisition from the thermal camera, using the relevant SDKs. The second pillar corresponds to the raw data preprocessing and filtering to a format acceptable for the third pillar which is in charge of extracting human shapes from the image, leading to the last pillar which acquires the segmented human shapes from the images and returns an estimate for the cartesian position of the operator.

An infrared camera placed on top of the ceiling of the workspace is used to detect and track the position of the operator within the workplace shared with the robotic manipulator. It is important, especially for soft safety HRC applications, to capture operator's position with high frequency rates, and with adequate accuracy. The utilization of such a sensor was made as the radiometric images captured offer the opportunity to easily extract the features of the human presence due to the temperature differences of the operator with his/her surroundings. Initially, during the designing phase the cell dimensions were evaluated to choose the proper sensor layout (infrared camera and its lens) that will be capable of supervising the whole desired area. Afterwards, due to the intrinsic difficulty of thermal cameras to estimate their extrinsic and intrinsic parameters, as in contrary to the conventional RGB cameras were the applied algorithms use visual patterns to calculate the camera matrix, an emulation of the visual patterns with thermal ones was implemented. Afterwards, the radiometric image received was processed to remove thermal noise from the field of view (scaling temperature values and using Gaussian blur implemented in OpenCV), while in addition small heat emitters such as devices were also removed. The binarization of the image follows, to create thermal blobs within the image (inside threshold values that correspond to human temperature each pixel will have a value 255 (white), otherwise the value would be 0 (black)). The operator detection follows, based on the size estimation of the thermal blobs viewed in the captured frames, as the number of pixels per blob is compared with specified values that represent humans; after finding thermal blob that represent humans. Then the calculation of their centroids is performed to acquire their position in the pixel space, while finally their values are transformed from pixel to cartesian space. The overall approach is summarized in Fig. 1, categorizing it in 4 main steps:

- Acquisition of radiometric data
- Image processing
- Human shape extraction and detection
- Human position estimation

More information is presented in Section 3.1.

Fig. 1. Approach of system's IR based human position detection.

2.2. Operator future trajectory forecasting

To deal with the uncertain nature of human motion, an approach employing Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs) was devised to predict the operator’s future trajectory, taking into account multiple causative factors. Through the collection of several datasets that record both the operator’s movements and the robot’s paths, a correlation was observed with the operator’s future position. During multiple cycles of operation, the movement of the operator displays regular or even recurring behavior. Therefore, past human positions, in conjunction with previous process variables, might be used to construct a prediction model strategy that performs time series forecasting. This multivariate model accepts multiple variables as input over multiple timesteps, creating a solution for a sequence-to-sequence problem. Notably, the proposed method is adaptable and may be applied with any type of sensor, as long as it can provide the operator’s torso coordinates. In this study, input data from thermal and RGBD cameras were utilized.

Initially, a simulation environment named Shopfloor Digital Representation (SDR) was created, which allowed the simulation of both human and robot movements. A synthetic dataset was generated, incorporating human motion data from numerous iterations of a specific HRC scenario. This scenario was then replicated several times in the real cell, producing a real-world dataset of human motion. Both datasets contain data about human movements and robot paths, correlated with the tasks being performed (Fig. 2 – data collection - training).

In the execution phase, the Future Trajectory Forecasting (FTF) module is used in tandem with the other software modules of the robotic cell. The process begins with the SDR module estimating the duration of the next robot task and asking the FTF to provide a prediction of the operator’s trajectory for a slightly longer duration (to accommodate potential delays in the new robot movement). The FTF receives data about the robot’s pose and the operator’s position to make the forecast.

The SDR then computes a robot trajectory that does not intersect with the operator’s future path and transmits it to the robot. FTF approach is illustrated in Fig. 2.

More specifically, Fig. 2 captures the following:

- i) Orange color: indicates the actions done for generation of a dataset using simulation data.
- ii) Green color: indicates the actions done for generation of dataset using a real-time execution data
- iii) Gray color: indicates the actions done for training of the model
- iv) Blue color: indicates the execution of the process using the FTF model.

More information is presented in Section 3.2 and Section 3.3.

2.3. Overall approach

The present work blends the outputs from the IR-based human tracking, the depth data tracking and the prediction model to achieve robot motion plans that aim to prevent collisions. The overall approach as depicted in Fig. 3 in three core layers; the first layers aims to detect the operator using multiple sensors. The motivation under thus choice is to guarantee that the operator is at all times detected (infrared cameras as in detail described in Section 3.1, and depth sensors as described in Section 3.3.2.). The second layer is in charge of evaluation operator positional data, and via deep neural network, to perform a prediction on what will be operator’s future motion. This data are shared via Robot Operating System (ROS) to the third layer, which is the digital twin and the integrated motion planners as obstacles, thus facilitating the generation of plans that prevent collision with human operators.

Fig. 2. Flowchart illustrating data acquisition, training, and FTF-enabled human-robot collaborative assembly.

Fig. 3. Human detection - Motion prediction - Motion planning approach to collision prevented plans.

3. Implementation

3.1. IR-based human tracking

3.1.1. Camera placement and calibration

The thermal camera chosen for the application, is the FLIR Boson 320 [27]. The considerations for choosing the proper sensor for the application were mainly based on the following parameters:

- Ability to capture the infrared radiation that human body emits.
- Given the camera positioning, the Field of View (FOV) of the chosen sensor should be capable of capturing the whole area required to be monitored.

As every object does emit electromagnetic energy and based on a spectrophotometrical examination, the maximum of the broad band of wavelengths that the energy is found to lie may be calculated by the Wien’s Displacement law (1):

$$\lambda_{max} = \frac{b}{T} \tag{1}$$

Where λ_{max} is peak wavelength the T is the absolute temperature and b is a constant of proportionality called Wien’s displacement constant. According to Barnes [28], the human skin IR emission wavelength emit by the human body has a maximum of $\lambda = 10 \mu\text{m}$. Given this, the Boson320 is capable of capturing sufficient infrared wavelengths from 7.5 to 12.5 μm , meaning it fulfilled the detection of human related temperatures for the specific application.

After determining the area that should be monitored by the camera, the required field of view can be calculated by the following Eq. (2) (3),

with the HFOV and VFOV being acquired by the manufacturer’s available lens options. (see Fig. 4)

$$L_{HFOV} = 2H \tan(HFOV/2) \tag{2}$$

$$L_{VFOV} = 2H \tan(VFOV/2) \tag{3}$$

HFOV, is the angle for horizontal field of view, the VFOV is the angle vertical field of view, L_{VFOV} is the length of the vertical field of view and L_{HFOV} is the length of the horizontal field of view.

Besides, the estimation of the camera parameters, both their extrinsics and intrinsics, are calculated as this process is of major importance for finally making accurate positional estimations. The extrinsic parameters are related to the cartesian pose of the sensor relative to the 3D scene and consists of a rotation R and a translation T matrix while the intrinsic parameters represent the optical and the focal length of the camera and consists of a matrix K . For the calibration process, the Zhengyou Zhang’s [29] calibration algorithm was utilized and implemented in OpenCV [30], and a chessboard specific for the thermal camera heated in the sunlight was used. The chessboard includes temperature differences within the checkerboard pattern as the black squares absorb more heat from the sunlight or from IR lamps and thus make their temperature higher than that of the white blocks.

In pixel space the coordinates of the pixels are described as $[u, v, 1]^{-1}$ and the feature points on the calibration board which are in the 3D scene have the coordinates $[X, Y, Z, 1]^{-1}$, though since the board’s surface is flat $X = 0$. Therefore, the relation between the pixels of the projected image and the calibration checkboard is given in Eq. (4):

$$s \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = K[R|T] \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}$$

Where RT is the rotation matrix and translation matrix from world-frame to pixel-frame, and K is the camera matrix. The radial distortion to correct the output image can be represented as per Eqs. (5), (6):

$$x_{distorted} = x(1 + k_1r^2 + k_2r^4 + k_3r^6) \tag{5}$$

$$y_{distorted} = y(1 + k_1r^2 + k_2r^4 + k_3r^6) \tag{6}$$

The tangential distortion to correct the output image can be represented as per Eqs. (7), (8):

$$x_{distorted} = x + [2p_1xy + p_2(r^2 + 2x^2)] \tag{7}$$

$$y_{distorted} = y + [p_1(r^2 + 2y^2) + 2p_2xy] \tag{8}$$

Where k_1, k_2, k_3, p_1, p_2 are the distortion coefficients. After the calibration process, the distortion coefficients (k_1, k_2, p_1, p_2, k_3) are estimated along with the camera matrix, that includes information like focal length (f_x, f_y) and optical centers (c_x, c_y) as per Eq. (9):

Fig. 4. Field of View (FOV) of a camera placed on the ceiling.

$$\text{camera matrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

In Fig. 5 the distorted and corrected/undistorted images are depicted.

3.1.2. Operator detection and cartesian position estimation

There are many difficulties while estimating the position of the operator with a 2D low resolution camera, as the pixel density is low, meaning that the camera discretizes the 2D plane in less big-sized surfaces. Taking all those into allowance, the process presented in Fig. 5 was implemented to return operator’s position with sufficient accuracy for our system.

Firstly, after the acquisition of the radiometric image data, the normalization of temperature values follows. To prevent potential high temperature differences from too cold or too hot objects that might be within the field of view of the camera, both a minimum and a maximum temperature threshold are set, thus keeping a stable imagery after the thresholding process. The acquired data as far as they represent temperature values are normalized in the range 0–255, taking as extreme values the threshold values described above, instead of the maximum and minimum temperatures within the sensor capture. The normalization Eq. (10) applied is the following:

$$\text{pixel_value}_{normal} = \frac{T_{value_per_pixel} - T_{min}}{T_{max} - T_{min}} \quad (10)$$

Where $\text{pixel_value}_{normal}$ is the normalized pixel intensity T_{min} is the minimum temperature value and T_{max} is the maximum temperature value and $T_{value_per_pixel}$ is the temperature value per pixel from the IR image.

In Fig. 6 an example of different threshold limits for the same image is depicted.

Following the image thresholding, a human temperature isolation (HTI) function was developed that aims to extract human temperatures from the captured frame, returning a threshold-ed, binary image. Prior to the thresholding, we tried to apply smoothing filters to achieve less noisy binary frames, though no significant improvement was noticed. Instead, it delayed the final detection having as a result to reject it. The HTI function scans through the pixels, checking for whether each one of them is between the accepted thresholds, as shown in Eq. (11). Fig. 7.

$$\text{pixel_value}_{bin} = \begin{cases} 0 & \forall \text{ pixel_value}_{normal} \in [\text{min}, \text{max}] \\ 255 & \forall \text{ pixel_value}_{normal} \notin (\text{min}, \text{max}) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Where pixel_value_{bin} represents pixel intensity value.

For smaller sized capture sections that may be heated or reflect radiation, further processing is performed, that based on the “blobs statistics” from the binary image, the operator’s shape can be extracted. A function scans through the detected heat blobs, and compares their size with a reference value, which represents an average of human thermal

blob; finally, the function returns a list of human sized shapes, composing a binary image without thermal noise. An example of the described image binarization is presented in Fig. 8, where thermal blobs from hot, electrical devices (such as monitors, computers etc.) that resemble human temperature in the thermal imagery are removed.

In the binary image where the human shape has been extracted and isolated, as the point of detection we regard the centroid of his/her amorphous heat shape. To perform this calculation, we utilized the calculation of the moments of the 2D blobs, which is a particular weighted average of image pixel intensities (12).

$$M_{ij} = \sum_x \sum_y x^i y^j I(x,y) \quad (12)$$

Where M_{ij} represents the moment of the blob, x,y refers to the row and column index and $I(x,y)$ refers to the intensity at that location (x, y) [50]. Afterwards, the pixel coordinates of the centroid are calculated using the following Eq. (13).

$$\{\bar{x}, \bar{y}\} = \left\{ \frac{M_{10}}{M_{00}}, \frac{M_{01}}{M_{00}} \right\} \quad (13)$$

To find the correlation of the pixels and cartesian coordinates, we apply the following Eqs. (14), (15) to acquire the relation between pixels and cartesian distances:

$$l_x = \frac{\text{number of pixels in x direction for a distance in x direction}}{\text{measure distance in x direction}} \quad (14)$$

$$l_y = \frac{\text{number of pixels in y direction for a distance in y direction}}{\text{measure distance in y direction}} \quad (15)$$

By knowing the relationship between pixels and actual dimensions, we convert the pixel coordinates having as reference the center of the image by applying the following Eqs. (16), (17).

$$\text{projection_pixels}_x = \text{image_width} * 0.5 - \bar{x} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{projection_pixels}_y = \text{image_height} * 0.5 - \bar{y} \quad (17)$$

Afterwards, the pixel coordinates are transformed to cartesian coordinates as per (18), (19) equations:

$$\text{projection_cartesian}_x = \text{projection_pixels}_x * l_x \quad (18)$$

$$\text{projection_cartesian}_y = \text{projection_pixels}_y * l_y \quad (19)$$

Due to the fact that those coordinates do not represent the actual position of the operator in the floor, but the projection of his/her chest in the 2D plane, we added an additional error variable that has a polynomial format, since the error increases in a non-linear manner as the detected operator steps away from the center of the camera. To estimate the factors of the polynomial, a depth sensor was utilized. The final position is estimated as per Eqs. (20), (21):

$$\text{correct_position}_x = \text{projection_cartesian}_x + \text{error}_x \quad (20)$$

Fig. 5. Distorted (left) and undistorted image (right).

Fig. 6. Human position detection steps using an IR sensor.

Fig. 7. IR captures for different threshold values.

Fig. 8. Blobs filtering in the binary image after threshold application.

$$correct_position_y = projection_cartesian_y + error_y \tag{21}$$

The results from the detection are presented in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9.

3.1.3. Comparison with YOLOv7

The presented methodology was also compared with YOLOv7 [31], not only to evaluate the detection capabilities, as YOLOv7, is one of the latest and best performing models for object detection, but also to check the run time processing power required in terms of CPU. To perform the

Fig. 9. Detection from paper's proposed method (left) compared to YOLOv7 (right).

afore mentioned comparison, a dataset consisting of 700 images was collected and split for train and test purposes in an analogy of 80–20%. The GPU was only used during the training phase of the model, to minimize delays. After the image’s annotation, the dataset was augmented as proposed from the available literature [32,33], to enhance the training process. As per the detection capabilities, in the test dataset both approaches demonstrated good results, performing accurate human detections. It is though important to point that the processing power required in the YOLO v7 approach, was significant larger, as it scored values ranging from 96.5% to 99.9% in CPU usage. In the contrary, the proposed thermal detection method scored values ranging from 9.9% to 12.4% for the same test video stream. The processor where the experiments were done was the Intel i7–1075 H. In Fig. 9 the detections from the two approaches are displayed. It is important to mention that the boundary box from the left image does not correspond to the detection boundary box, as its size is fixed based on the white dot which indeed is the actual detection placed onto the operator’s body, indicating the centroid of the human shape in the binary image.

3.2. Synthetic dataset generation in a simulation environment using A*

3.2.1. Shopfloor digital representation – human motion simulation

The Shopfloor Digital Representation (SDR) primarily concentrates on the simulation and creation of robot movement, alongside replicating the operator’s motions within a virtual setting. This setting is an exact mirror of the actual environment. The SDR framework incorporates various tools, including the MoveIt! planning framework [34]. In this paper, our primary focus is on the SDR subcomponent responsible for emulating human movement.

3.2.2. Two-Dimensional (2D) projection of cell – search grid formation

The planning system that generates the operator’s path conducts a heuristic search within a 2D grid, as will be further analyzed in Section 3.2. The objects projected onto the 2D map might be either static or dynamic. Static objects remain stationary, and their projections are made only once during the initialization phase; such objects are worktables, columns etc. On the other hand, dynamic objects can change multiple positions or/and poses during a cycle, like robots. The grid is an “m x n” matrix with values ranging from 0 to 100. Accessible or unoccupied grid cells have a value of 0, while restricted or occupied cells carry a value of 100. Moreover, the map is generated with respect to a predefined reference frame, specifically the base of the robot. This means that the elements of the 2D grid matrix incorporate two known values - the x and y coordinates of the reference frame. The procedure for projecting the robot onto the 2D map is outlined below:

Primarily, the robot’s link positions serve as a reference to construct

a rectangular volume around the links (see transforms in Fig. 10). The coordinates, transposed from the robot’s base link, corresponding to the 2D plane that parallels the structured map, are associated with a matrix element that has a smaller distance, as shown in Fig. 10. For simplicity, the distance comparison is executed separately for rows and columns, reducing computational complexity from $O(n^2)$ to $O(n) + O(n)$. After projecting the points, a sorting algorithm organizes the points within the matrix map in a clockwise pattern. Subsequently, a polygon-filling algorithm is employed, facilitating a conceptual representation of the robot on the 2D grid (Fig. 10).

People do exercise caution and prefer maintaining a certain distance from robots [35], so the robot’s projection is expanded using a technique commonly used in image processing. This expansion of the robot’s projection is achieved by applying a 2D Gaussian blur filter [36], where each element of the array is convolved with a Gaussian kernel, then all the elements are summed to generate the output array. To mitigate computational complexity in a 2D matrix, the 2D Gaussian blur can be implemented using two separate 1D Gaussian blurs (for rows and columns), resulting in a computational complexity of $2 * O(n)$ rather than $O(n^2)$. Fig. 11 represents the aforementioned application of the Gaussian blur. The rationale in using the Gaussian filter is the utilization of a computationally efficient expansion of robot project with a reducing occupancy from the actual obstacle onto the 2D map, preventing human simulated paths from being too close to the robot projection.

3.2.3. Human trajectory planner and controller

The human trajectory planner utilized in the simulation environment, is based on the A* algorithm to generate human trajectories. The heuristic function is based on the Euclidean distance estimation between neighboring nodes [37]. It uses a normalized input from the map values, ranging from [0100] to [0,1], to assess the transit difficulty from the parent node (n_p) to the child nodes (n_c). Each transition along an axis is valued at 1 during the shift from n_p to n_c . The role of the human motion controller is to carry out the trajectory generated by the A* planner. Given the dynamic changes in the map, objects may intersect or come near the preplanned path. Consequently, the controller’s task is to execute one node movement at a time, ensuring that no obstacles interfere with the planned trajectory. To counter the memory complexity challenges stemming from the A* algorithm, the search grid discretization value was subjected to numerous experiments, and areas of the grid that would not contribute to a path solution were designated as obstacles. The Chebyshev distance [38] was chosen for the cost function, as movement along the 2D map has eight possible transitions (horizontal, vertical and diagonal). The human trajectory planner aims to provide the controller solely with valid, unimpeded paths as illustrated in Fig. 12, in less than ~100 ms.

Fig. 10. Frames correlation (left) and frame projection in the 2D map (right).

Fig. 11. Robot's projection in the 2D map: without gaussian filter (left) with gaussian filter (right).

Fig. 12. Human trajectory simulation using A* pathfinding algorithm, within the RVIZ [48] environment.

3.2.4. Synthetic dataset generation

The simulation execution is launched initializing all the resources that are involved in the process (poses, process stage etc.). The tasks assigned to the robot correspond to specific poses and tool actuations, similar to those for the human operator. Upon completing a task, the human operator is directed to the next position. In alignment with real-life situations, this position will not intersect with the robot's path and will not always remain constant. To introduce variability in both the x and y directions, a normal distribution is applied. It's crucial to eliminate irregularities in the dataset, specifically "zigzag" movements due to the 2D grid discretization and mimic the sensor noise encountered in real-time human position estimation. For this purpose, a polynomial interpolation was implemented in the synthetic dataset to smoothen human trajectories. Specifically, the Lagrange interpolating polynomial $P(x)$ of degree $\leq (n - 1)$ that passes through the n points $(x1, y1 = f(x1)), (x2, y2 = f(x2)), \dots, (xn, yn = f(xn))$ was employed. Additionally, stochastic noise following a normal distribution was introduced to the human dataset, mimicking the acquisition deviations of the Azure Kinect sensor in narrow field of view mode, as demonstrated by experimental results in [39]. With the induction of this noise, the dataset closely approximates the real sensor acquisitions, enhancing the realism of the simulation.

3.3. Implementation of a deep learning network for human future trajectory prediction

3.3.1. Modelling approach

The proposed A* implementation could be utilized for the prediction model in real-time as a planning-based method, though it was not selected due to several issues, such as memory complexity, lack of guaranteed response time and strict task-oriented execution, that are not ideal for this soft safety application. In contrast, the proposed RNN model, which belongs to the pattern-based category, is more suitable for complex environments with complicated, unspecified dynamics, enabling predictions without strict task-oriented inputs. Pattern-based methods are highly dependent on the specific case, as they depend on statistical behavioral patterns of the acquired operator's trajectories, though with ample data collection, good results may be achieved [26]. The adequacy of the data is very important as apart from the common patterns, the function approximator (in the specific case the RNN) may also learn infrequent patterns too, as those might occur from rare robot planning. Data adequacy also corroborates the utilization of synthetic datasets derived from simulations, as they may run a great number of iterations in a small amount of time.

3.3.2. Human tracking using Azure Kinect

To perform accurate human detection that will guarantee that operators are tracked consistently within the workspace and their position is shared redundantly to the prediction model, an additional sensor layout was added to the thermal camera detection system, including two Azure Kinect depth cameras. The sensing network is designed to detect human operators by analyzing both 2D image and depth data collected. Each point cloud undergoes processing via the body tracking algorithm, leading to the evaluation of the human body index map for various human joints. Subsequently, the positions and orientations of human articulations are selected based on the confidence values determined by the algorithm. The approach described above is illustrated in Fig. 13.

To begin with, the efficient placement of sensors is crucial, as it facilitates more precise detection and evaluation of the operator’s joint positions and orientations. Given the availability of two RGBD sensors, they were strategically positioned at a fixed 90 degrees relative rotation. This orientation mitigates the problem of occlusions that may occur when the operator’s body blocks the view of certain joints from the camera, such as when the operator stands sideways.

Since multi-sensor support through the official Microsoft Azure Kinect ROS driver was under development at the time of the study, we have modified the driver’s source code for our research to enable simultaneous utilization of both sensors. The node responsible for publishing the raw sensor data and body tracking evaluations shares the information from each sensor to two separate topics. The driver initiates both cameras using their unique serial numbers, allowing for data segregation based on these numbers. To access the data shared by the sensors, the translational and rotational transformations between the camera frames should be applied to the published data. This data is then further transformed to the necessary world/global frame, as demonstrated in Fig. 14, using human joints as an example.

Ensuring the precise identification of the translational and rotational placement of the sensors is crucial. This is achieved through the extrinsic cameras’ calibration, resulting in a uniform point cloud. The calibration process, which identifies the transformation of the camera’s coordinate system relative to a predefined frame, involves two steps:

- Camera position estimation using a fiducial marker.
- Estimation refinement via the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) [49].

A fiducial marker, which possesses a specific pattern easily identifiable by computer vision applications, was used in this case. We employed an AprilTag [40] marker, recognizable by the OpenCV vision library. Iterative Closest Point (ICP) is an algorithm that iteratively minimizes the geometric difference between two sets of points by estimating the optimal transformation. The Open3D [41] open-source library was utilized, as it already implements ICP. After applying the ICP algorithm, the errors are minimized, resulting in a uniform point cloud.

The Azure Kinect Body Tracking SDK was used for 3D detection of the human operator. This software can accurately detect and track multiple humans using deep learning techniques. The two-sensor layout is beneficial as it broadens the monitorable area and, with proper placement, yields more accurate human joint detections in instances of occlusions.

The accuracy of the depth sensor’s human body tracking depends on various factors. As highlighted in this study [39], the camera’s field of view settings significantly impact detection accuracy. WFOV has higher error values compared to NFOV within the common reachable FOV. Moreover, the distance from the sensor is a critical factor. If the human is too close to the camera or near the limits of the FOV, the detection may be unachievable or compromised in terms of accuracy [39]. Taking these factors into account, we selected a combination of the Azure Kinect sensors’ available FOVs to cover the entire workspace. The WFOV monitors the wide length of the orthogonal area, while the NFOV monitors the smaller side.

The operator’s joint positions are captured using the Azure Kinect Body Tracking SDK and the Azure Kinect ROS driver. The data is returned as a visualization_msgs/MarkerArray.msg ROS message (each marker in the MarkerArray represents one of the 32 joints detected by the AKBT SDK). This ROS object contains all the information regarding the joints’ orientation and transformation relative to the RGBD sensor. A slight modification was made within the driver to add the sensor’s confidence values to the "alpha" instance of each Marker.

Fig. 13. Body tracking approach using depth sensors.

Fig. 14. Transforms among world frame, sensors frames and human joints.

To fuse the body tracking data estimated by each sensor, we implemented the algorithm illustrated in Fig. 15. Initially, we checked whether the person being tracked was detected in the common sensors' FoV. If the operator was only detected by one sensor, the body tracking data from that sensor was used to represent their joints. If the human was detected by both sensors, the joint values were assigned by comparing their confidence scores and their linear measure from the sensors. The estimated values were then used to fill the final human message for sharing within the ROS nodes.

3.3.3. Real dataset acquisition and processing

As stated earlier, the proposed method is not bound to any specific

sensor type used for human tracking, as long as it may estimate the position of the human torso relative to a known reference frame of the work cell. In this instance, we employ a sensor network comprising: i) an RGBD camera, and ii) an infrared (IR) camera situated on the ceiling of the shop floor. The general strategy involves integrating two distinct detection methods. The Kinect sensor, known for its precision, is given priority over the basic infrared (IR) sensor for estimating the operator's position. However, if one tracking method fails to locate the operator at a given time, the system defaults to using the other sensor. This flexible approach ensures continuous and accurate tracking regardless of individual sensor limitations. Data collection was performed using the ROS [42] framework over several iterations. The finalized dataset is a.csv file

Fig. 15. Fusion of body tracking data by the 2 depth sensors.

containing human torso (x, y) coordinates and robot joint state poses, associated with the tasks executed. We opted for a simplified (x, y) representation of human position rather than a bounding box for two reasons: i) this streamlined approach supports a broader array of sensors, particularly those that only provide average human position, as multi-joint 3D position estimation is not universally supported beyond depth sensors and IMUs, ii) once the operator's forecasted trajectory is acquired, the bounding box can be generated within the digital twin environment where robot trajectory planning occurs.

Datasets may contain noisy acquisitions, including false or missing data. To address these issues, a series of preprocessing steps were implemented. First, missing sections in the dataset, which could result from temporary detection loss, were identified and filled by linearly interpolating values between the preceding and subsequent elements. Next, the process of identifying and removing outliers was conducted. The mean value and standard deviation of the (x, y) human position coordinates were calculated, and outliers were detected using the z-score. The identified outliers were replaced by interpolating the mean of adjacent prior and subsequent values to maintain data continuity. To further filter the noise from the human dataset, the Savitzky-Golay (SavGol) filter [43] was applied. This filtering technique is based on the least-squares fitting of local polynomials in the time domain. The SavGol filter effectively preserves the shape and width of the signal while effectively removing noise, resulting in noise-free coordinates that accurately represent the human's position, with preserved peak characteristics.

3.3.4. Prediction model structure and integration

The forecasting model takes into account several parameters, including operator position, robot pose, and the tasks executed during each cycle. It utilizes multiple previous timesteps to predict the human's future trajectory over several upcoming timesteps, making it a multivariate and multistep prediction model. The structure of this model is based on a multi-layer LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) neural network, which effectively captures long-term temporal dependencies in the input data during the training phase. Fig. 16 illustrates an example of this, where the floor grid coordinates (x and y axes) and timestamp values (z-axis) depict the datasets, revealing recurring patterns of human movement represented by a gradient from yellow to blue. In the right picture in Fig. 16 the operator's recorded trajectories are depicted.

For making predictions with variable-length inputs and outputs, an LSTM-based Encoder-Decoder model was employed. The encoder interprets the input sequences, and its output serves as input for the decoder, which generates outputs for each required timestep in the output sequence. To achieve forecasts at each step in the output sequence, the decoder incorporates an additional LSTM output layer encased in a Time Distributed wrapper. To further enhance its forecasting capabilities, a bidirectional layer wraps the encoder's LSTM layer, enabling the model to learn sequences bidirectionally. The deep

learning network was implemented using the TensorFlow library [44]. The model is depicted in Fig. 17.

A server-client based architecture was established to distribute the predicted path from the FTF module to the rest components of the system. The FTF server receives the operator's position and the robot's pose from the process ROS nodes. The incoming message is segmented into a matrix containing past and current acquisitions separated by a pre-defined timestep, which the predictive model is trained for. The data is then input into the RNN for forecasting, and the predicted path is shared within the local network. The time estimated for both communication and prediction is approximately 65 ms.

The predicted trajectory of the operator, by evaluating his/her anthropomorphic characteristics, such as height and shoulder length, generates 3D collision objects for each one of the trajectory points, as shown in Fig. 18. Thus, the SDR with its robot path planners perceive in 3D space the cell's fixtures, the operator's initial and future-predicted positions and then generates a path avoiding collisions with the aforementioned entities. The robot executes its motion upon a high-level orchestration system that commands the robot to perform its operations, and the evaluation is performed one time before every motion request. The path planning and the integration of the collision objects are handled by MoveIt! motion planning pipeline and how this work is out of the scope of the paper.

To deal with the occurrence of an overlapping robot goal with the FTF forecast, robot speed is modulated to reduce the possibility or the impact of an imminent collision; the robot starts the execution of its motion, and when it reaches the 75% of its trajectory, the collaborative speed is reduced from 250 mm/s to 175 mm/s.

3.3.5. Synthetic and real datasets utilization

The simulation environment, along with the generated synthetic dataset, were utilized during the development phase of the prediction model. They facilitated the replication of a real-world process execution without the need for a physical cell, thus allowing for testing and refinement of the FTF model.

Additionally, FTF was improved by running the model derived from the synthetic dataset (SDPM) in parallel with the model derived from the real-time dataset (RDPM). To achieve this, an additional testing dataset was collected, and both SDPM and RDPM were evaluated based on their forecasted trajectories compared to the actual ones. The Modified Hausdorff Distance (MHD) was used to measure the geometric similarities between the trajectories. Upon comparing the mean MHD for the forecasted trajectories, it was observed that in certain instances the SDPM performed better than the RDPM, since the synthetic dataset encompassed patterns not found in the real dataset. To combine both SDPM and RDPM, the average scores of the models are estimated and compared depending on which areas of the workplace they perform better. Thus, when the FTF performs a prediction, the position of the operator is taken into allowance to use the model that performed the

Fig. 16. Visualization of temporal dependence of input data.

Fig. 17. Encoder-Decoder LSTM model with bidirectional layer.

Fig. 18. Volumetric recreation of operator's future trajectory, representing 3D obstacles for the robot path planner.

best in the respective area.

4. Case study

4.1. Case study description

To demonstrate the human detection method with the thermal camera, an application derived from the sector of renewable energy was utilized. The assembly of a solar thermal collector panel is performed by operators who install several small components and finetune the panel's surface. The repeatability of the processes, as handling along with assembly operations are numerous within a shift, combined with the panel's significant weight (between ~42–50 kg and two operators are required to handle it), raises ergonomic concerns and symptoms such as fatigue or back pain. What is more, as the time passes within the shift, the difficulties of carrying such large weight decreases cycle time and consequentially production efficiency.

4.2. Robotic solution description

The robotic solution includes the first high payload collaborative robot (COMAU AURA) [45] which is used as smart work holding device, that takes on the strenuous tasks of manipulating the heavy part around, presents it to the operator, and holds it until the overall process is complete, in a user centric manner [46,47]. The role of the operator is based on the dexterity and flexibility that characterizes him/her, to complete the assembly and combined with the collaborative robot the cycle time is maintained without delays from fatigue or discomfort. The HRC solution leverages the capabilities of the first high payload collaborative robot in the market, known as COMAU AURA. In this intelligent setup, the robot serves as an advanced work holding device. It efficiently picks up the heavy solar panel from the previous production station and strategically presents it to the operator in the most convenient manner [46]. The worker then proceeds to install smaller, intricate components like stickers, small pipes, and sealing rings, requiring dexterity. Throughout the process, the robot continuously adjusts its position to facilitate seamless component placement, and once the assembly

is complete, the robot stores the finished product in a storage pallet. For a visual representation of the HRC task sequence, refer to Fig. 19.

The robot is equipped with a contact sensitive skin and with a tool collision detection system, thus enabling Power and Force Limiting (PFL) HRC, with active safety robot dynamics, guaranteeing the operators' safety in workspace sharing conditions. Additionally, the cell is monitored with safety (certified) and standard (not certified) rated sensors: i) SafetyEye [4], a Performance Level "d" (PL"d") - Category "3" (cat"3") sensor ensures the operator safety according to ISO standards, as this might not be guaranteed in cases of not safety rated sensors (RGBD and IR cameras) were update rate is not high and rarely some acquisition might be missing, ii) standard sensors (IR and depth sensors) allow accurate positional tracking of the operators for non-safety critical use (Fig. 20). The installation of safety systems, both for monitoring and contact sensing is of critical importance, as it works as a fallback in cases of undesired robot planning, unexpected human behavior or inaccurate human motion forecasts.

4.3. Experimental process

To assess the effectiveness of our approach, we conducted an experiment involving seven operators (comprising 4 males and 3 females) aged between 20 and 37 years. Each participant was tasked with assembling the panel under two experimental configurations:

- In the first configuration, the assembly was performed without the assistance of FTF (Future Trajectory Forecasting). In this scenario, the robot trajectory was generated in real-time using the SDR module, which considered only static obstacles during its planning.
- In the second configuration, the assembly was conducted with the aid of FTF. The position of the operator was tracked using an IR and RGBD camera, allowing FTF to estimate the operator's trajectory for the next few seconds. Meanwhile, the SDR module generated the

Fig. 19. Human - Robot task sequence.

Fig. 20. High-payload collaborative workstation paradigm, depicting real life scene (upper left), digital twin (upper right), thermal camera-based human detection (lower).

robot trajectory, accounting for both static obstacles and the predicted future trajectory of the operator (a process that takes <1 s).

As presented in Fig. 19 the robot trajectories where the potential human-robot contact may occur, are four: i) one to pick the panel, ii) one to present the panel to the worker, iii) one to readjust panel presentation enabling the completion of the assembly and iv) one to place the panel in the storage pallet. Each participant underwent a total of 70 iterations, repeating each experimental configuration five times with alternating sequences.

In each iteration, both the number of safety violations and the cycle time were meticulously recorded. A safety violation was defined as occurring whenever the separation distance between the robot and the operator fell below a specific threshold value, which was approximately 1.88 m in this particular case study, adhering to ISO directives. In such instances, the robot’s movement was immediately halted. Additional safety violation is when the operator touches the robot’s safety contact system, causing the robot to stop.

To gauge the effectiveness of our approach in building trust in the high payload robotic solution, the operators were requested to provide subjective feedback in the form of questionnaires. They were asked to rate their level of approval both before and after the activation of the prediction feature during the robot planning phase. This rating was given on a scale of 0 to 10. A comprehensive summary of the results can be found in Table 1, presenting the outcomes of these assessments and feedback from the operators.

4.4. Results and discussion

The results clearly indicate that the proposed approach had a significant positive impact on the cycle time, leading to reduced cycle times for all operators (approximately 6%) owing to a substantial decrease in safety violations (approximately 75%). This is justified, as whenever the robot stops because of a collision event with an operator or a safety violation in general, it takes at least 3 s to restart, which increases the total time needed to complete tasks, thus leading to cycle time increase. The inclusion of the FTF, due to generation of collision prevented robot paths, prevents such occurrences significantly reducing the number of collisions.

Table 1
Experimental results.

	Cycle time (in min ['] and sec [''])		Safety violations (lower is better)		User approval (higher is better)	
	w/o FTF	with FTF	w/o FTF	with FTF	w/o FTF	with FTF
Operator A	6'52"	6'24"	7	2	6	7
Operator B	6'26"	6'09"	6	1	6	6
Operator C	6'37"	6'24"	4	2	7	8
Operator D	7'11"	6'38"	6	0	6	8
Operator E	6'02"	5'51"	3	1	7	7
Operator F	7'06"	6'42"	8	2	6	7
Operator G	6'14"	6'01"	5	2	6	6

Most subjects expressed that the introduction of FTF heightened their sense of trust, as they observed that the robot no longer intentionally moved towards them, enhancing the overall perception of safety. The users also highlighted that when the robot was moving towards them this made them feel uncomfortable, while knowing also that the robot was capable of understanding human existence and estimate their intention as a safety proactive measure, increased their confidence and their safeness feeling. Regarding user approval, it is important to note that the nature of the process itself plays a crucial role. Since operators are not accustomed to close coexistence and collaboration with high payload robots, the increase in user approval was modest but still notable, with an average increment of approximately 0.7 out of 10. This highlights the significance of the positive impact of the proposed approach in enhancing user confidence and acceptance, despite initial unfamiliarity with such collaborative robotic systems.

It is crucial to highlight the significance of the integrated detection system, which combines a thermal camera and a depth sensor. This setup, particularly due to the infrared sensor being mounted on the ceiling, enables the detection of operators even during occlusion incidents. Such occurrences could be when the operator is obscured by the robot, manipulated components, or surrounding elements. Maintaining

consistent human detection is paramount as it ensures the accurate predictive performance of the FTF system, thus driving improved adjustment of robot behavior.

5. Conclusion and outlook

This research presents a solution aimed at enhancing the efficiency and safety of HRC cells. This study explored the use of an infrared camera sensor to detect and track the operator's position in an HRC workspace, with a minimal computational load. The tracking system is further augmented with the integration of a depth sensing system for increased accuracy. Additionally, the paper introduced an AI tool designed to forecast the future trajectory of operators within these HRC cells, with the aim of supporting the system's trajectory planners in reducing the risk of potential collisions between robots and operators. This was achieved by predicting operator movements, enabling planners to design robot paths that act as a soft safety measure to prevent robot path intervention with humans. The AI tool includes a methodology for generating synthetic datasets using simulations, and it is easy and flexible to integrate with multisensory systems and advanced robot trajectory planners.

The integration of these two technologies, AI-based trajectory prediction, and infrared tracking showed promising results, with a demonstrated reduction of safety violations by about 75% and an improvement in cycle time by nearly 6% in the studied scenario. This also led to increased separation between robots and operators, resulting in an increase in operator trust levels.

An important issue that should be further studied in future work, is handling unforeseen human behavior. Patterns that are not included within the datasets are difficult to be predicted by the RNN. Even though physics-based predictive models are capable of minimizing false forecasts, the time horizon of the prediction is limited. Planning based methods from the other side, are highly task oriented, and it is difficult to include human preferences as those might be captured in real-life datasets. Thus, it is essential to perceive the prediction model as a soft safety addition and ensure that the collaborative robotic system fulfills all the safety requirements for the application (safety dynamics, contact detection, speed and separation monitoring etc.).

In the future, further research involves a more detailed study regarding the correlation between synthetic and real-life data, tests of various Neural Network algorithms and the development an ensemble learning model to enhance prediction accuracy. An additional focus will be placed on incorporating more sensors for increased accuracy along with sophisticated sensor fusion algorithms and integrating AI-enhanced features for accurate human detection. Furthermore, the adaptability and scalability of this combined solution across different industrial settings and robot configurations will be thoroughly examined. Moreover, the ROS industrial will be utilized to advance towards a certifiable solution. The measurement of user acceptance may be obtained through a sensing system that evaluates heart rate and brain activity, while trust might be assessed using formal methods suggested by the literature for human trust in machinery. To tackle the challenge of false predictions, we may explore producing multi-model predictions from different categories such as physics-based and planning-based models. What is more, additional testing and comparison with existing human motion prediction approaches will be examined.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sotiris Makris: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Christos Gkrizis:** Software, Formal analysis, Data curation. **George Michalos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **Konstantinos Katsampiris-Salgado:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Nikos**

Dimitropoulos: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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